

ISSUES OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL
THEATER IN EUROPE

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Annotation: The formation of musical theater in Europe has led to the wide spread and development of this direction throughout the world. The article deals with the formation and development of the European musical theater.

Key words: Theater, art, European culture, drama, opera, modern play, musical theater, actor.

Annotatsiya: Yevropada musiqiy teatrning shakllanishi ushbu sohaning dunyo bo'ylab keng yoyilishiga va rivojlanishiga sabab bo'ldi. Maqolada yevropa musiqiy teatrining shakllanish va rivojlanish masalalari haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Teatr, san'at, yevropa madaniyati, drama, opera, zamonaviy spektakl, musiqali teatr, aktyor.

Аннотация: Становление музыкального театра в Европе привело к широкому распространению и развитию этого направления во всем мире. В статье рассматриваются вопросы становления и развития европейского музыкального театра.

Ключевые слова: Театр, искусство, европейская культура, драма, опера, современная пьеса, музыкальный театр, актер.

The history of the cultural development of mankind cannot be imagined without the ancient theater. It is known that the ancient theater originated as a theater of grandiose ideas related to the life and fate of people. In ancient Greece, Aeschylus, Sophocles, Euripides, Aristophanes, and in Rome Plautus and Seneca sang the beliefs of passionate love and gratitude to the Motherland through new stage forms,

generalized philosophical and profound artistic images. From the ancient world we received incredibly beautiful, highly artistic literary samples of the genres of tragedy and comedy. During the Renaissance, which began in the 15th century, the ancient traditions of artistic creativity were re-mastered in Italy, the theater of a new era was founded. The first tragedies, comedies, theoretical treatises on the dramatic art of the Renaissance were born here. A little later, the Spanish theater and, finally, on the example of Shakespeare's work on the soil of England, the European theater rises to the highest stage of its development. The theater of French classicism of the 17th century appeared longer [1, 4-p.]

Theatrical rudiments were created and improved in different periods in connection with the formation and development of theatrical art in the countries of the East and West, in many cases within the disciplines of history, philosophy, literary studies. Theoretical generalization of theatrical practice appeared in Greece, Rome, India, China. Aristotle's "poetics" is the first experience of the theory of art, including drama and theater. The study of drama and theater in Western Europe began with the study of ancient manuscripts of the Renaissance. In England of the 16th century, humanists wrote a number of scientific works defending the role and aesthetic value of theatrical art in moral education. The theory of drama develops as a separate direction. Theater criticism of the 18th century is also beginning to develop. In the 2nd half of the 19th century, the scientific method and principles of theater were established in England. The scientific basis of theater in Germany was laid in the 18th century: it began with the research of I. K. Gottscheid. In the late 18th and early 19th century, Goethe and Schiller made an important contribution to the development of theater. In the 2nd half of the 19th century, many theatrical works, memoirs, and bibliographic sources were published. Since the 1990s, special theater courses have been taught at the universities of Bonn and Leipzig, and theater research institutes have been established in Cologne and Kildare. In 1902, the Society for the Study of Theater History was established in Berlin. In France, the theater was clearly manifested in the work of the writer and philosopher D. Diderot (18th century). In the second half of the 19th and early 20th

centuries, fundamental studies on the history of theater, drama and acting were created. In 1933, the Society for the History of the Theater was established in France. In Russia in the 19th century, P. I. Sumarokov, A. Pushkin, N. Gogol, V. Belinsky and others made a great contribution to the development of the theater. In 1939, the Institute of Theater, Music and Cinematography was established in St. Petersburg. In the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, a number of Uzbek theater critics defended their candidate and doctoral dissertations at these universities. Within the framework of the former Soviet Union, monographs and articles about the Uzbek theater were published among other national theaters. Here we can highlight the merits of O.Olidor (Kaidalova), M.Grigoriev and others.

In America, musical theater performances of the mid-18th century included rough variety revue, which eventually turned into vaudeville, minstrel shows that soon crossed the Atlantic and Britain, and Victorian burlesque, first popularized in the United States by British troupes. A theatrical play in English, corresponding to the modern concept of a musical, with the addition of dance and original music that helped tell the story, is usually considered a Black Fraud, which premiered in New York on September 12, 1866. The production lasted a staggering five and a half hours, but despite its duration, 474 performances were held in it - record-breaking, in no small part because of the scantily clad female ballet choir. In the same year, *The Black Domino / Between You, Me and the Post* became the first show to call itself a "musical comedy". Comedians Edward Harrigan and Tony Hart produced and acted in musicals on Broadway between 1878 (*The Mulligan Guards Picnic*) and 1885, with a book and poems by Harrigan and music by his father-in-law David Bram. These presented comedies feature characters and situations taken from the daily lives of the lower strata of the New York City population, they represent a significant step from burletta, minstrel shows, pop and musical situations to more legitimate theatrical forms. They played high-class singers (Lillian Russell, Vivien Segal and Faye Templeton) instead of ladies with dubious reputations who played in ancient more musical genres.[2]

As you can see, the concept of "musical theater" in different national traditions and among different scientists and theater figures has different connotations. It is necessary to recognize the correctness of the German musicologist K. Blumröder, who noted that musical theater is "terminologically an extremely problematic category" [Blumröder 1990, 30]. However, this statement refers to the turn of the 1980s and 1990s. At that time, there were no attempts to give a dictionary definition of musical theater in the foreign scientific literature.⁶ After only a few years, attempts to deal with the ambiguous concept have already appeared. But up to the present time, researchers have stated its semantic polyvalence. One thing remains indisputable: the term "musical theater" is the brainchild of the twentieth century and the processes in artistic life that it generated.

Processes related to the awareness of a new theatricality and a new connection or the possibilities of communication between music and the stage. It was this new consciousness that turned the phrase into a buzzword, but at the same time led to semantic discord, which was caused by the action of multidirectional vectors.[3]

The history of musical culture in England is distinguished by its peculiar originality. One of the first countries in Europe, England became famous for its polyphonic singing. This is evidenced by the classic examples of folk polyphony that have reached our time. The ancient genres of English folk music include the so-called epic and heroic ballad songs created by bards - poets and singers. In the distant past, professional composer creativity arose, and the experiments of musical and theoretical studies began.

In post-war English music, the tendency is dominated by the centrifugal need to look at the world with a wide-eyed look. The younger generation resolutely came into contact with the innovative search of European masters - Stravinsky, Schoenberg. At the origins of "Fasta" by William Walton (1902-1983) are compositional ideas drawn from Schoenberg's Lunar Pierrot, but the basis of the stylistics of the work is anti-antiquism, proclaimed by Stravinsky and the French Sixes. Constant Lambert (1905-1951) surprised compatriots, from the very first steps on his career began to work in

the genre of ballet, the traditions of which were interrupted in England in the second half of the XVIII century; in fact, it is quite natural that the composer was attracted by this genre, which became in Europe by the 20s of the 20th century a symbol of modern artistic pursuits. Lambert's Romeo and Juliet ballet (1925) was a peculiar response to Stravinsky's Pulcinella. At the same time, his other composition - Elegiac blues for a small orchestra (1927) - Lambert responded to the jazz that hit the European players. Alan Bush (1900-1995) linked his activities with Eisler's creative position and the workers' movement; he not only took in the corresponding socio-political and philosophical ideas, but also developed his composer technique, drawing on the experience of Novovenskaya school, which was fruitfully refracted by Eisler. [4]

In the English musical culture of the 1st half of the 18th century, the activity of G. F. Handel played a major role. Handel lived in London for about 50 years (1710-59). He easily adapted to the tastes and artistic requirements of the English public, creating over 40 operas in the Italian style (performed by the London troupe in Italian). The German composer became the center of the musical life of England. This was facilitated not only by Handel's bright creative personality, his performing skills, but also by the energy of the organizer, the democratic orientation of his searches. Handel's influence was especially evident in choral music. In his oratorios based on ancient, historical and biblical heroic plots ("Judas Maccabee", "Samson", "Israel in Egypt", etc.), for the first time the struggle for the freedom-loving ideals of humanity was embodied in musical images.

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